

ON THE ADHESIVE PROPERTIES OF NANO-SILICA/EPOXY BONDED SINGLE-LAP JOINTS

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ABSTRACT

The effects of nano-silica on the adhesive properties of epoxy were systematically studied by single lap-shear tests under quasi-static and cyclic loadings. The adhesives were manufactured from different amount of nano-silica particles incorporated into diglycidyl ether of bisphenol-A (DGEBA) epoxy. Quasi-static tests were conducted on single lap-shear joints at ambient, with and without exposure to 100% relative humidity at 60°C for different times. Cyclic tests were also performed on these bonded joints under tension-tension loading. The fracture surface morphology was investigated by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) to identify the failure mechanisms. Compared to neat epoxy, it was found that the presence of nano-silica particles significantly improved the adhesive properties of epoxy under all testing conditions.

1 INTRODUCTION

Epoxies have been widely used in many engineering applications including as adhesives for aircraft parts, anti-corrosive coatings in pipes, and underfill in electronic packaging among others. However, their moderate strength and low toughness are limiting their use in many situations. Hence, in bonding and joining of structural components, surface pre-treatments of the adherend [1] and incorporation of fillers in epoxy adhesives [2] are most common ways to address these issues. Surface pre-treatments are complicated and often involve chemical reactions which need good process control. By contrast, the addition of rigid or soft fillers into the adhesive is a simple solution. Many previous studies have explored the benefits of nano-fillers relative to micro-fillers on the mechanical properties of polymers [3]. The size of the nano-fillers approaches the chain gyration radius of the polymer macromolecules. Thus, the interface area is orders of magnitude higher than micro-fillers at the same loading. These two factors determine the performance of the composites. Our previous work [4] has shown that nano-silica particles can improve the Young's modulus, yield strength and fracture toughness of neat epoxy. In this study, nano-silica was used as fillers in epoxy to enhance the adhesive properties.

Bonded joints fail when the adhesive strength is exceeded during service. Herein, we measure the adhesive strength under quasi-static loading when the joints are dried and after hygrothermal treatment in 100% relative humidity (RH) at an elevated temperature (60°C) to evaluate the hygrothermal effect, since epoxy-based adhesives are susceptible to moisture absorption [5,6]. In our previous work [7,8] on tensile fatigue and mode I fracture energy of bulk nano-silica/epoxy, we found that these nanoparticles increased the fatigue lifetimes and decreased the crack growth rates of the epoxy.

However, few studies have reported the cyclic fatigue performance of nano-silica/epoxy as adhesive. Therefore, we also study the cyclic loading effect on adhesive strength. Finally, the fracture surfaces of the adhesively bonded joints after all mechanical tests are studied by scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Sample preparation

Epoxy resin, bisphenol A diglycidyl ether (DGEBA), Araldite F, and hardener, a cycloaliphatic secondary amine, Piperidine, were supplied by Sigma-Aldrich, Australia. Silica nanoparticles in the form of master batches with 40 wt.% concentration in DGEBA resin, Nanopox F 400, were obtained from Evonik Hanse GmbH, Germany. These surface modified spherical silica particles were formed *in situ* through sol-gel processing within the resin, yielding an average size of 20 nm and a very narrow particle size distribution which would not change during further blending. Modifications on the silica surface enabled crosslinking with epoxy resin during curing and prevented agglomeration in the matrix. Some basic properties of Araldite F and Nanopox F 400 are listed in Table 1.

Table 1 Characteristics of epoxy resin and nano-silica master batch.

Material	Epoxy equivalent weight (EEW) (g/eq)	Density@20°C (g/mol)	Viscosity@25°C (mPa.s)	SiO ₂ content (wt.%)
Araldite-F	185	1.18	2000	0
Nanopox F 400	295	1.4	60000	40

By mixing plain DGEBA resin with the required amounts of nano-silica master batch, epoxy-based composites with different filler loading could be obtained. The amount of curing agent was calculated to ensure the weight ratio with epoxy was 1:20. Plain epoxy resin and nano-silica master batches were heated up to 80°C to reduce the viscosity and mixed thoroughly by mechanical stirring. These samples were degassed in vacuum at -100 kPa and 80°C for 4 h to remove traces of humidity and air bubbles. The curing agent was added while stirring slowly after evacuation. The mixture was subsequently used as an adhesive for bonding tensile single lap-shear joints, ensuring no air bubbles inside the mixture. The samples were then cured at 120°C for 16-22 h, after which, they were allowed to cool gradually in the oven to ambient temperature. These preparation procedures were identical to our previous study on toughening mechanisms of nano-silica/epoxy [4]. Observation under transmission electron microscopy (TEM) showed the nanoparticles having a homogeneous distribution in the epoxy matrix at all loading. Four material systems for single lap-shear testing were prepared: (a) neat epoxy (E); (b) 10 wt.% nano-silica/epoxy (S10); (c) 20 wt.% nano-silica/epoxy (S20); and (d) 40 wt.% nano-silica/epoxy (S40).

2.2 Measurements of adhesive properties

Many test standards exist for characterizing adhesives and their bonding strengths. One commonly used method is the tensile single lap-shear test, which is easy to conduct and resemble closely the type of loading in structural adhesives during service. Here, we followed the single lap-shear test standard ISO 4587-1979. The specimen geometry for the tensile lap-shear test is shown in Fig. 1. Stainless steel plates (25×100 mm²) were chosen as adherends due to their high modulus and strength compared to the nano-silica/epoxy adhesives. They were cut from the same steel panel to maintain same chemical and physical surface properties, ultrasonically cleaned in acetone, washed with distilled water and dried. Two steel plates were bonded with the adhesives on an overlapping area of 12.5×25 mm². The thickness of the adhesive layer was ~0.28 mm, being controlled by inserting short copper wires of similar diameter inside the bonded area. The length and amount of copper wires used did not affect the adhesive property.

Quasi-static tensile single lap-shear tests were performed on an Instron 3366 machine with a 10 kN load cell at ambient conditions. All test specimens were located symmetrically in the grips; the long

axis of the specimens coincided with the direction of the applied force through the centerline of the grip assembly. The load was applied at a constant rate of 1.0 mm/min and a typical load-displacement record for a tensile lap-shear test is shown in Fig. 2. Lap-shear strength was calculated by dividing the fracture load with the bonded area. At least five similar tests were conducted and the average result was reported for each individual group.

Fig. 1 Specimen geometry for tensile lap-shear test (all dimensions in mm)

Fig. 2 A typical load-displacement plot of quasi-static tensile lap-shear test

Single lap-shear joints were exposed to 100% RH at 60°C in a close chamber for different periods of up to 3 weeks, dried for 24 h at 60°C and tested at ambient to determine the residual adhesive strengths after the hydrothermal treatment.

Load-controlled tension-tension fatigue tests with stress ratio of 0.10 were conducted on the single lap-shear samples in an Instron 8800 testing machine. The maximum cyclic stress used varied from 0.3 to 0.8 of the quasi-static failure strength. All tests were conducted at 1 Hz with a sinusoidal waveform.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Effects of nano-silica on adhesive strength of lap-shear joints

Fig. 3 shows the results of tensile lap-shear tests for E, S10, S20 and S40 with average adhesive strength of 17.83, 21.34, 21.52 and 19.41 MPa (standard deviation less than 1.28 MPa), respectively. The influence of nano-silica on adhesive strength is similar to what was observed in [9]. At 10 and 20 wt.% of nano-silica, the adhesive strength is improved by 20%; but at a higher loading of 40 wt.%, the adhesive strength is decreased since the high viscosity has worsened the substrate wettability with the adhesive [10].

Fig. 3 Relationship between filler content and failure strength by tensile lap-shear test

Fig. 4 (a) Typical paired failure surfaces of a single lap-shear joint; and (b) schematic showing crack propagation in a lap-shear test (not to scale). (Arrows indicate self-equilibrated forces applied on the lap-shear samples)

Fig. 4a shows typical failure surfaces of a sample after the tensile lap-shear test. Owing to the high stress concentration at the edges of the adhesive layer [11], cracks initiate from both ends and grow towards the middle leading to final failure, Fig. 4b. To study the failure mechanisms of neat epoxy and nano-silica/epoxy bonded joints, crack initiation sites on paired or matching failure surfaces (see red circled areas in Fig. 4a) were observed by SEM (Zeiss Ultra Plus Field Emission). We take S10 as representative of the nano-silica/epoxy adhesive bonded joints. Figure 5 shows paired SEM images of the failed joints, E and S10, and black arrows indicate the shear direction. Several comments can be made: (a) Fig. 5f shows the morphology of the steel adherend (without adhesive) with surface cracks or crevices into which the adhesives can penetrate. (b) There are clear differences between these two bonded joints. The failure surface of S10 (Fig. 5c) is much rougher than E (Fig. 5a), which reflects the much more intense plastic deformation of S10 compared to E. (c) From the paired SEM images of S10 we can identify the major failure mechanisms. Fig. 5c shows highly deformed ridges of S10 adhesive peeled away from the surface cracks/crevices of the steel adherend leaving behind the broken parts on the paired side in Fig. 5d. This is encouraged by the high peeling stresses at the fracture initiation sites. Also, debonding/pullout of nano-silica particles can be seen in Fig. 5e for S10. All these deformation mechanisms dissipate large amounts of energy [12], leading to higher adhesive joint failure strength. Fig. 5d exhibits a thin layer of S10 adhesive on the fracture surface indicating the joint fails cohesively. (d) It is obvious that in E the paired SEM images, Figs. 5a and 5b, show matching failure features with epoxy peeled from the surface cracks/crevices of the steel substrate. By comparing Figs. 5b and 5e and noting the different surface characteristics it seems that a very thin layer of E adhesive is present in Fig.

5b suggesting cohesive failure near the interface has occurred. Nonetheless, regions of adhesive failure (see red arrows) can also be observed. Further work is required to clarify this.

Fig. 5 SEM images of paired failure surface of lap-shear joints of (a,b) E and (c,d) S10. (e) Failure surface of S10 (region marked by blue arrow) showing debonding and pullout of nano-silica particles; and (f) surface morphology of steel substrate (without adhesive). (Black arrows indicate shear direction applied on the sample surfaces).

3.2 Hygrothermal effect on residual adhesive strength of lap-shear joints

The residual strengths of hygrothermally treated adhesive joints, E, S10 and S20, were measured at ambient conditions and the results are shown in Fig. 6. Clearly, the adhesive joint strength decreases with increasing exposure time with a remarkable drop in the first week. After three weeks, the average joint strengths are 11.3, 12.6 and 12.9 MPa for E, S10 and S20, respectively. Indeed, for all exposure

durations, nano-silica/epoxy adhesives outperform neat epoxy adhesive after hygrothermal treatment. Previous study [13] showed that an adhesive layer with a thickness of 0.12 mm could not achieve full saturation even after 182 days in water at 50 °C. This result helps explain the fast degradation of the residual adhesive strength after the first week and slow degradation in the next two weeks as shown in Fig. 6. But the degradation mechanisms leading to the reduced joint strengths have not been studied.

Fig. 6 Lap-shear joint failure strength *versus* hygrothermal treatment time

Fig. 7 Paired SEM images of failure surfaces of lap-shear samples after hygrothermal treatment for (a,b) E and (c,d) S10. (Black arrows indicate shear direction applied on sample surfaces)

Paired SEM images of the failed joints for E and S10 are shown in Fig. 7. Several observations are given below: (a) Hygrothermal treatment has smoothed the failure surfaces relative to those without such treatment. This can be proven by comparing the surface morphologies of Figs. 7a versus 5a for E and Figs. 7c versus 5c for S10. (b) The sharp ridges of S10 adhesive peeled from the cracks/crevices of the steel adherend in Fig. 5c have become much less prominent in Fig. 7c. However, within the ridges and in the region marked by a blue arrow, unlike in Fig. 5e, no nano-silica debonding/pullout can be found. (c) Comparing the paired SEM images of S10 (Figs. 7c, d), joint failure is mainly cohesive with few visible adhesively failed areas (see red arrows in Fig. 7d). By contrast, in case of E, Fig. 7b does not show the presence of neat epoxy adhesive on the failed surface but resembles the steel surface in Fig. 5f. This may indicate dominant adhesive failure in E due to an adverse hygrothermal effect.

3.3 The influence of cyclic fatigue on lap-shear joints

Cyclic fatigue test results on single lap-shear joints, E, S10 and S20, were analysed in terms of the applied stress amplitude (S) versus number of cycle (N) curves. Shenoy et al. [14] mentioned two distinct regions in the S-N curve in single-lap joints fatigue testing: the crack initiation domination was found at lower fatigue loads whereas crack propagation dominated at higher fatigue loads. Further, the visual microscopic observation from [15,16] showed that the fraction of the crack initiation phase in the whole fatigue life was in the range from 20% to more than 70% depending on the stress level. As suggested by Basquin [17], the relationship between the applied stress amplitude, σ_a , and number of load reversals to failure, N_r , is:

$$\sigma_a = \sigma_f N_r^b \quad (1)$$

where σ_f and b are fatigue strength coefficient and exponent, respectively. The number of reversals to failure N_r is related to the number of cycles N_f ($N_f \gg 1$):

$$N_r = 2(N_f - 1) \approx 2N_f \quad (2)$$

Fig. 8 shows log-log plots of experimental results of fatigue tests on single lap-shear joints, E, S10 and S20, according to Eq. 1 and from which we can determine σ_f and b for these joints. Thus, (σ_f, b) are (20.76, -0.110) for E, (26.84, -0.108) for S10 and (19.89, -0.074) for S20. Clearly, S10 and S20 have much longer lifetimes than E under the same applied cyclic maximum stress.

Fig. 8 Relationships between applied stress amplitude σ_a and number of reversals to failure N_r for E, S10 and S20

4 CONCLUSION

This study has systematically investigated the adhesive properties of single lap-shear joints bonded by epoxy and nano-silica/epoxy at ambient conditions under quasi-static loading, including the influence of hygrothermal exposure to 100% RH at 60 °C, and cyclic loading. Incorporation of 10 and 20 wt% of nano-silica into epoxy improves the adhesive joint strength by 20%. Hygrothermal treatment does not change the beneficial effect of having nano-silica than neat epoxy on the adhesive joint strength. In cyclic fatigue, for given applied stress amplitude, the lap-shear joints with nano-silica/epoxy adhesives have longer lives than those with only neat epoxy adhesive.

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